

Relationship Of Lower Limb Anthropometry Profile, Vertical Jump Performance And Aerobic Capacity Amongst The Recreational Basketball Players: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Background: Basketball performance is influenced by a combination of physical, physiological and anthropometric factors. The main objective of this study was to summarize the findings of vertical jump performance, aerobic strength, and anthropometric characteristics of the lower limbs in recreational basketball players in order to understand their collective role in player selection and development.

Materials and Methods: Articles published in peer-reviewed journals between 2015 to 2024 focusing on young basketball players or university-level recreational players were included in this review study. The main outcome measures were vertical jump performance, aerobic capacity, or anthropometric indicators of the lower limbs. A systematic search was conducted across databases such as PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar. Keywords included "vertical jump performance," "aerobic capacity," "anthropometric measurements," and "basketball players". Five free full-text articles were identified through PubMed and Google Scholar, adhering to objectives and inclusion criteria.

Results: The findings consistently demonstrate that both physiological and anthropometric factors significantly influence basketball performance in recreational players. Aerobic and anaerobic power were identified as key determinants of sprint performance.

Discussion: This literature review summarizes the available evidences regarding the relationship between the anthropometric profile, vertical jump performance and aerobic capacity amongst the basketball players. Due to lack of databases, limited evidences were synthesized. Systematic review utilizing extensive database can be conducted in future to validate the current findings.

Conclusion: This literature review concluded that vertical jump performance and aerobic capacity, alongside anthropometric measurement provide a basis for refining player selection and development strategies, particularly for youth athletes.

Keywords: Vertical jump performance, aerobic capacity, lower limb anthropometric measurements, recreational, basketball players

INTRODUCTION

Basketball is one of the most widely played and spectated team sports globally, characterized by its fast pace, intermittent high-intensity demands, and complex technical requirements [1]. According to the Federation International de Basketball (FIBA), basketball ranks as the second most popular sport

worldwide, highlighting its extensive participation across different age groups, competitive levels, and recreational settings [4]. The duration and structure of basketball games vary depending on competition level, age category, sex, and governing federation, resulting in diverse physiological and physical demands placed on players [4]. Modern basketball is distinguished by a high degree of

athleticism, technical variability, rapid transitions, and frequent physical contact, requiring players to repeatedly perform explosive movements such as sprinting, jumping, rapid deceleration, and directional changes.

At competitive levels, basketball players are exposed to intense training loads and competitive pressure from a young age, largely due to the sport's stringent performance requirements and talent identification systems [5]. Consequently, identifying determinants of performance has become a priority in basketball science. Anthropometric characteristics such as body height, body mass, limb length, shoulder breadth, and muscle girths have been widely recognized as critical factors influencing performance and playing potential [6]. Somatotype and anthropometric profiling are frequently used as selection criteria, particularly in youth development programs, as they provide valuable insights into physical suitability for the sport.

Despite the strong emphasis on elite performance, recreational basketball has received comparatively limited scientific attention. This lack of focus is notable given that recreational basketball is widely practiced and has been shown to confer significant health and fitness benefits [8]. Data on young men participating in recreational basketball are particularly scarce, creating a gap in the literature regarding their physical fitness characteristics and performance determinants. University students represent a particularly relevant population for investigation, as evidence suggests that enrollment in higher education is associated with a marked decline in physical activity levels and physical fitness [9]. Understanding how recreational basketball participation influences fitness parameters in this population is therefore of both scientific and public health interest.

Physical fitness refers to the ability of the body to maintain physiological homeostasis during physical exertion and to rapidly restore equilibrium during recovery [7]. In basketball, physical fitness encompasses multiple components, including aerobic capacity, anaerobic power, muscular strength, speed,

agility, balance, and coordination. The intermittent nature of basketball requires players to repeatedly alternate between high intensity anaerobic actions and periods of lower-intensity aerobic recovery, making both energy systems essential for optimal performance [9,10]. Consequently, basketball players typically demonstrate superior aerobic and anaerobic conditioning compared to non-athletes and untrained individuals [8].

Numerous studies have examined the relationships between physical fitness components and basketball performance. Aerobic capacity, maximal oxygen consumption, sprint speed, agility, and anaerobic power have all been shown to play significant roles in game performance and training adaptation. Fitness testing batteries are commonly employed to assess these characteristics and to monitor training outcomes in both competitive and recreational players. However, variability in testing protocols and participant characteristics continues to limit comparability across studies, emphasizing the need for population-specific research.

Basketball performance is multifactorial and influenced by a complex interaction of skill-based, anthropometric, physiological, physical, and psychological variables [12]. Technical skills such as shooting, passing, and dribbling must be executed efficiently under conditions of fatigue, physical contact, and time pressure. Physical attributes such as height, limb length, muscle strength, and power further modulate the effectiveness of technical execution, particularly during actions such as rebounding, shot blocking, and jump shooting. Psychological factors, including competitive instinct, decision-making, and stress tolerance, also contribute substantially to performance outcomes [14].

Among the physical actions performed in basketball, the vertical jump is one of the most frequently executed and performance-relevant movements. Vertical jumping is integral to rebounding, shooting, blocking, and rapid acceleration during gameplay [3]. The vertical jump shares biomechanical similarities with other explosive lower-limb movements,

making it a widely accepted indicator of lower-body power. As a result, vertical jump performance is commonly used in basketball research to evaluate neuromuscular function and athletic potential [2].

Recreational basketball players, although not exposed to the same training volumes as elite athletes, still perform repeated jumping and high-impact movements that place substantial demands on the musculoskeletal system. Impaired balance and stability during landing after jumping have been identified as common mechanisms underlying lower-extremity injuries in basketball. Balance ability is therefore a critical component of basketball performance, particularly given the sport's high frequency of sudden stops, rapid direction changes, and physical contact situations. Studies have reported significant relationships between balance ability and both basketball playing ability and technical performance. Poor postural control during dynamic tasks may compromise movement efficiency and increase injury risk, especially during landing and cutting maneuvers. Anthropometric characteristics and lower-limb strength further influence balance performance, suggesting that physical profiling may assist in identifying players at greater risk of injury or reduced performance efficiency [17].

Anthropometric and physiological profiling has long been used to differentiate basketball players from nonplayers and to identify positional demands within the sport. Research has shown that basketball players generally exhibit superior aerobic fitness, agility, flexibility, and reaction time compared to age-matched controls [13,20]. Additionally, maturation status and training experience have been shown to significantly influence aerobic fitness and physical performance in youth basketball players [19].

This review aims to identify consistent patterns, key performance determinants, and existing gaps in the literature, thereby providing a clearer understanding of how these physical and physiological factors collectively influence basketball performance and player development in non-elite settings.

OBJECTIVES

The objective of this literature review is to critically summarize existing literature examining the relationship between lower-limb anthropometric characteristics, aerobic capacity and vertical jump performance in recreational basketball players with a particular focus on young and university-level populations.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Previous research has demonstrated significant associations between vertical jump performance and anthropometric characteristics such as body height, body mass, limb length, and lower-limb muscle girths [15,18]. Lower-limb strength and peak torque have also been shown to correlate positively with vertical jump height, further highlighting the role of muscular power in basketball-specific performance [16]. Differences in vertical jump force-time characteristics have been observed across age groups and competitive levels, reflecting variations in neuromuscular development and training exposure [5].

While elite and youth competitive basketball have been extensively studied, recreational basketball participation remains under-represented in the literature. Recent studies have begun to highlight the positive effects of recreational basketball on aerobic capacity, respiratory efficiency, and overall physical fitness among university student [8]. Furthermore, correlations between speed, agility, vertical jump performance, and shooting precision have been reported in recreational basketball players, emphasizing the relevance of physical fitness even at non-elite levels [3].

Further demonstrated associations between foot posture and vertical jump performance in adolescent recreational basketball players, underscoring the importance of biomechanical and anthropometric factors in jump performance. These findings suggest that even subtle variations in physical characteristics may influence performance outcomes in recreational populations [1].

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

This literature review focused on synthesizing existing evidence related to lower-limb

anthropometry and physical fitness parameters relevant to basketball performance. A comprehensive literature search was carried out using electronic databases including PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar. Articles published between 2015 and 2024 were considered. Inclusion criteria included articles published in English language ; articles available as full text ; articles involving recreational basketball players and articles analyzing anthropometric profile, vertical jump performance and aerobic capacity. Exclusion criteria included review studies, periodicals, conference proceedings, articles involving

professional basketball players. The search strategy employed combinations of the following keywords: vertical jump performance, aerobic capacity, anthropometric measurements, lower limb anthropometry, and basketball players. Full-text articles were assessed for eligibility according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Following this screening process, five studies that closely aligned with the objectives of the review were selected for final inclusion. Table 1 describes the PICOS parameters used in this literature review.

Table 1: PICOS parameters utilized in this literature review

Population	Recreational Basketball Players
Intervention / Exposure	Vertical Jump Performance, Anthropometry , Aerobic Capacity measurement
Comparison / Control	Conventional Training
Outcome	Aerobic performance, Sprint ability, Anthropometry variables, jumping ability
Study Design	Experimental Study, Correlational Study, Cross- Sectional Study, Observational Study

Due to heterogeneity in study designs, participant characteristics, and assessment protocols, a qualitative narrative synthesis was adopted. Findings were summarized descriptively, focusing on patterns and relationships between anthropometric variables, aerobic capacity, and vertical jump performance in recreational basketball players.

Search strategy and Data Collection:

Figure 1 summarizes the search strategy including identification, screening and inclusion of relevant studies. In this literature

review a total of 490 studies were identified following keywords search via different databases like Google Scholar, Scopus and PubMed. After duplicate removal 200 studies remained, during screening process title and abstract were screened for 290 studies, following 100 records were excluded. Full text articles sought for retrieval were 190 out of 90 reports were not retrieved. 100 reports were assessed for eligibility out of which 95 were excluded. Finally, 05 studies were included in this literature review.

Figure 1: Flowchart of the search strategy

RESULTS

Characteristics of the Included Studies:

Table 2 describes the characteristics of the included studies. This literature review comprises of five studies, out of which two were experimental studies, two were correlational studies and one was observational study. The included studies were conducted in different countries namely, Turkey, Germany, India, Italy and Nigeria. The main outcome measures which were assessed were aerobic capacity, anthropometry profile and vertical jumping performance.

Table 2: Characteristics of the Included Studies

Author; Year; Country	Sample Size (S); Research Design (RD)	Objective	Methodology	Outcome Measures	Results	Conclusion
Aslan & Ziyagil et al., 2020, Turkey ^[9]	S:586; RD: Observational study	To analyze variation in physical and energy system capacities	Sprint and power testing	Aerobic/Anaerobic powers, sprinting ability.	Sprint ability influenced energy system capacities	Aerobic & anaerobic powers significantly influenced sprinting performance.

Aschendorf et al., 2018, Germany ^[11]	S:24; RD: Experimental study	To examine effects of basketball-specific HIIT	Training intervention with fitness testing	Aerobic performance	Significant improvement after training	HIIT improved aerobic capacity and basketball-specific performance.
Meshram et al., 2018, India ^[13]	S:60; RD: Experimental study	To assess aerobic fitness	Aerobic fitness testing	Aerobic fitness (VO ₂ max)	Players showed good aerobic fitness	Basketball players had significantly higher aerobic fitness.
Altavilla et al., 2018, Italy ^[14]	S:74; RD: Correlational study	To examine relationship between anthropometry and jump ability	Anthropometric and vertical jump assessment	Anthropometry and jumping ability with Bosco & Abalakov tests	Significant association observed	Role-based differences in jump performance linked to height and reach.
Aiyegbusi et al., 2017, Nigeria ^[15]	S:112; RD: Correlational study.	To assess role of lower-limb anthropometry in vertical jump	Lower-limb measurements and jump tests	Lower limb anthropometry and vertical jump.	Significant correlations observed	Leg length, muscle strength, body composition critical for jump height.

Abbreviations:

HIIT – High-Intensity Interval Training

VO₂ max – Maximal Oxygen Consumption

Additional Analysis:

1. Vertical Jump Performance amongst the recreational basketball players

Vertical jump performance was the most consistently assessed indicator of lower-limb explosive power across the reviewed studies. Recreational basketball players were commonly evaluated using field-based tests such as the countermovement jump (CMJ), squat jump (SJ), and Abalakov jump, while a limited number of studies employed force-platform analysis to assess force-time characteristics. Field-based jump tests demonstrated good feasibility and applicability in recreational settings, allowing assessment of neuromuscular performance with minimal equipment [1,4,14].

Studies incorporating force-platform measurements provided additional insight into jump mechanics, revealing age- and maturation-related differences in peak force, rate of force development, and impulse generation [5]. Older and more mature recreational players exhibited superior force-time profiles, indicating improved neuromuscular coordination and muscle-tendon efficiency. These findings suggest that vertical jump height alone may underestimate performance differences, and that kinetic analysis offers a more sensitive assessment of neuromuscular function.

Biomechanical factors also influenced jump outcomes. Pronated foot posture was associated with reduced vertical jump height, likely due to altered force transmission and compromised stability during the propulsion phase [1,17]. Furthermore, studies reporting correlations between vertical jump performance and speed, agility, and shooting

precision reinforce the functional relevance of jump capacity in basketball-specific tasks [3,4]. Overall, vertical jump testing remains a valid and practical tool for performance monitoring in recreational basketball players, particularly when combined with biomechanical and strength assessments.

2. Anthropometry profile amongst the recreational basketball players

Anthropometric assessment across the reviewed literature primarily included measurements of body height, body mass, body mass index, limb length, lower-limb girths, wingspan, and body composition. These variables were frequently used to evaluate physical suitability for basketball participation and to identify performance-related advantages in recreational players [6,9,11].

Height and limb length emerged as influential factors in jump performance and shooting-related outcomes, particularly in youth and university-level players [6,10,13]. Greater lower-limb girth and lean muscle mass were consistently associated with superior vertical jump performance, highlighting the role of muscle cross-sectional area in force production [11,14,15]. In contrast, higher body fat percentage showed a negative association with jump height, likely due to increased non-functional mass affecting power-to-weight ratio [13].

Anthropometric profiling also revealed positional tendencies, with guards generally displaying lower body mass and greater agility, while forwards and centers exhibited greater height, reach, and power-oriented characteristics [10,16]. However, variability in measurement techniques and limited reporting of standardized protocols reduced comparability across studies. Despite these limitations, anthropometric assessment remains a low-cost, non-invasive, and valuable screening tool for performance evaluation and talent identification in recreational basketball populations.

3. Aerobic Capacity amongst the recreational basketball players

Aerobic capacity was commonly assessed using VO_2 max estimation tests, field-based endurance tests, and respiratory efficiency measures. Recreational basketball players consistently demonstrated superior aerobic

fitness compared to untrained individuals, reflecting the intermittent high-intensity nature of basketball activity [7,12,19].

Studies reported that recreational basketball participation improves cardiorespiratory efficiency, with enhanced oxygen utilization and recovery capacity during repeated high-intensity efforts [7]. Aerobic fitness was also shown to interact with sprint ability and anaerobic power, emphasizing the integrated contribution of aerobic and anaerobic systems during basketball performance [9]. Players with higher aerobic capacity demonstrated improved tolerance to fatigue, allowing sustained execution of technical skills such as jumping and shooting during prolonged play.

Training-based investigations further supported the trainability of aerobic capacity in recreational players. Basketball-specific high-intensity interval training produced significant improvements in aerobic performance, reinforcing its relevance for conditioning programs even at non-elite levels [8]. Nevertheless, inconsistencies in testing protocols and reliance on estimated rather than directly measured VO_2 max limit the precision of current findings. Standardized aerobic assessment methods are therefore warranted to improve comparability and practical application.

Collectively, these additional analyses indicate that vertical jump performance, anthropometric characteristics, and aerobic capacity are interrelated components of basketball performance in recreational players. Vertical jump assessment provides insight into neuromuscular power, anthropometric profiling identifies structural advantages and limitations, and aerobic capacity assessment reflects the ability to sustain repeated high-intensity actions. Integrating these assessments offers a more comprehensive understanding of performance capabilities and supports individualized training and development strategies in recreational basketball populations.

The review from the five studies demonstrated that both physiological and anthropometric factors play a significant role in basketball performance, particularly in sprinting ability, aerobic capacity, and vertical jump performance.

Sprint performance has been shown to be strongly influenced by underlying energy

system capacities. Specifically, both aerobic and anaerobic power were identified as key determinants of sprinting ability in recreational athletes, indicating that sprint performance is not solely dependent on anaerobic mechanisms as traditionally assumed [9]. High-intensity interval training (HIIT) tailored to basketball-specific movements has been found to significantly enhance aerobic performance and overall physical capacity in players. Following a structured HIIT intervention, participants demonstrated marked improvements in aerobic fitness, suggesting its effectiveness in conditioning programs for basketball athletes [11].

Aerobic fitness levels among basketball players were observed to be considerably high, with significant VO_2 max values reported in experimental settings. These findings highlight the importance of aerobic conditioning in supporting sustained performance during gameplay [12].

Anthropometric characteristics were also found to have a strong association with performance outcomes, particularly vertical jump ability. Variables such as height, limb length, and reach showed significant correlations with jump performance, with positional differences observed among players [13].

Similarly, lower-limb anthropometry, including leg length, muscle strength, and body composition, demonstrated a significant relationship with vertical jump performance. These findings emphasize the critical role of structural and muscular characteristics in determining explosive lower-limb power [14].

DISCUSSION

The present review highlights that basketball performance is a multifactorial construct influenced by the interaction of physiological capacities, training adaptations, and anthropometric characteristics. The findings consistently demonstrate that both aerobic and anaerobic energy systems contribute significantly to performance outcomes, particularly sprinting ability and repeated high-intensity efforts.

Traditionally, sprinting and explosive movements in basketball have been predominantly associated with anaerobic metabolism. However, the findings included in this review indicate that aerobic capacity also

plays a substantial role in sprint performance [9]. This may be attributed to the intermittent nature of basketball, where repeated bouts of high-intensity activity are interspersed with short recovery periods. A well-developed aerobic system enhances recovery between these bouts, thereby indirectly supporting sprint performance and reducing fatigue over the duration of the game. This challenges the oversimplified view that sprint performance is purely anaerobic and emphasizes the need for integrated energy system training.

The effectiveness of basketball-specific high-intensity interval training (HIIT) further supports the importance of combining aerobic and anaerobic conditioning. The observed improvements in aerobic performance following HIIT interventions suggest that sport-specific conditioning protocols can simultaneously target multiple physiological systems [11]. This is particularly relevant in modern basketball, where players are required to sustain high work rates, execute rapid transitions, and maintain performance consistency throughout the game. HIIT, when designed with sport-specific movements, appears to bridge the gap between laboratory-based conditioning and real-game demands.

In addition to training adaptations, the review underscores the importance of baseline aerobic fitness in basketball players. High VO_2 max values reported among players indicate that aerobic conditioning is not merely supplementary but essential for optimal performance [12]. Enhanced aerobic capacity contributes to improved endurance, faster recovery, and better tolerance to fatigue, all of which are critical during prolonged gameplay. This reinforces the idea that conditioning programs should not neglect aerobic development, even in sports characterized by short bursts of activity.

Anthropometric characteristics were also found to significantly influence performance, particularly in relation to vertical jump ability. Variables such as height, limb length, and reach were positively associated with jumping performance, with notable differences observed across playing positions [13]. These findings suggest that certain physical attributes may provide a biomechanical advantage, especially in tasks involving reach, rebounding, and shot-blocking. However, it is important to recognize that while

anthropometry can influence performance potential, it does not solely determine it. Skill level, neuromuscular coordination, and training also play crucial roles.

The role of lower-limb anthropometry and muscle characteristics further reinforces the importance of structural factors in explosive performance. Significant relationships between leg length, muscle strength, body composition, and vertical jump height highlight the contribution of both mechanical leverage and muscular force production [14]. Players with favorable limb proportions and higher muscle mass are likely to generate greater force and power output, resulting in improved jump performance. This has practical implications for talent identification and position-specific training.

Taken together, these findings emphasize that basketball performance cannot be attributed to a single factor. Instead, it is the result of a complex interaction between physiological capacity, training methodology, and inherent physical characteristics. From a practical standpoint, this suggests that training programs should adopt a holistic approach, integrating aerobic conditioning, anaerobic power development, and strength training tailored to individual anthropometric profiles.

However, there are limitations that must be considered. Variations in sample size, study design, and assessment methods across the included studies may affect the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, most studies focus on isolated variables, whereas actual performance in basketball is influenced by technical, tactical, and psychological factors as well. Future research should aim to integrate these aspects to provide a more comprehensive understanding of performance determinants. Systematic review utilizing extensive database can be conducted in future to validate the current findings.

CONCLUSION

This literature review concluded that anthropometry, vertical jump performance and aerobic capacity are inter-related to each other. Anthropometric characteristics influence vertical jump performance in recreational basketball players, with body composition showing the most consistent associations. Lower body fat and greater lean mass tend to

enhance jump outcomes, while the effects of height, body mass, and limb lengths are more variable across studies. Aerobic capacity is consistently related to the vertical jump performance amongst the recreational basketball players. The included studies were limited and are heterogenous in nature, so any firm conclusion cannot be drawn. However, more studies are required to confirm the existing findings.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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